

The moderating role of knowledge assets in measuring the impact of intellectual capital of financial performance

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Abstract

Present day associations fabricate get to and sustain knowledge assets to make upper hand. Physical and financial assets have been overshadowed by knowledge assets to make esteem expansion for association there by making feasible "knowledge advantage". Explore in intellectual capital includes ID, comprehension and measuring of the concealed elements like intellectual capital, human capital and social capital so on. Defenders of intellectual capital research opine that these imperceptible variables influence the performance of organizations. This paper surveys the expository way to deal with measuring the esteem creation effectiveness of intellectual capital. The review measures relationship between organization's intellectual capital and financial performance.

Keywords: Capital Finance, Impact of Intellectual, role of knowledge

1. INTRODUCTION

Ascent of the 'new economy' mainly determined by knowledge and data has made an immense enthusiasm for intellectual capital (Thurow, 1999; Petty and Guthrie, 2000 and Stewart, 1997). Investigate in Intellectual capital (IC) includes the mission in understanding the utility of IC and its part in affecting the financial performance. IC can be characterized as intellectual assets that have been "formalized, caught and utilized" to make assets of higher esteem (Prusak, 1998). While getting tuned to the new financial reality of change into knowledge economy, it is coherent to regard IC as an asset than as a cost (Pulic, 2004). In the time of knowledge economy, organizations deliver items and administrations, as well as are discovering approaches to make esteem expansion and riches from their own particular assets to fabricate practical business associations. Today, organizations envision themselves as learning associations and comprehend that knowledge assets upgrade development and assume a key part in enhancing business performance. Rumelt (1984) keeps up that both substantial and elusive assets are potential key assets. Asset based perspective of the firm includes the upsides of both substantial and impalpable assets. This hypothesis has increased wide acknowledgment in bookkeeping, financial and administration writing as it has possessed the capacity to give positive outcome linkages between assets of firms and measures of performance (Canibano, 2000).

Despite the fact that numerous immaterial assets don't discover a place in the rundown of essential key assets, IC is for the most part considered as significant since it involves particular and important knowledge exclusively having a place with an association. There has been a blast of intriguing reviews on IC since Stewart distributed an article on "Mental aptitude" (Stewart, 1991) The organizations contending in the knowledge based economy should be esteemed distinctively since conventional measures of bookkeeping may not suffice. Researchers are of the view that conventional measures of financial performance are insufficient to esteem knowledge firms. Organizations need to enhance their revelation and revealing of IC and esteem creation techniques. (Edvinsson, 1997)

The outcome presents confirm on the connection between IC and financial performance by embracing PLS – Path Modeling strategy. At last this review presents confirm on the effect of IC on financial performance and its prescient capacity concerning two ventures considered. Additionally, the discoveries help unsophisticated financial specialists to better comprehend the changing face of business and reasonableness of utilizing IC for assessing business performance.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Current writing on IC, hypothesis system and estimation discover its cause from bookkeeping and financial viewpoints, concentrating on the firm level investigation (Bontis N, 2000) Researches over the globe have attempted to depict the idea of IC and its constituents. The fight for acknowledgment of IC as a critical idea for surveying present day associations has been generally won.

2.1. Definition of IC

There are different definitions for IC. Specialists have attempted to characterize and investigate distinctive aspects of IC. In any case, the general sign is that IC is a non-money related asset without Physical presence yet has esteem that can produce future income. Barney (1991) opines that IC is something which is elusive and is a noteworthy vital asset equipped for producing supportable upper hand and prevalent financial performance. Stewart (1997) characterized IC as "bundled valuable data". He has additionally expressed that IC could be seen as knowledge, data, intellectual property, encounter that can be put to use to make riches. Ramstad and Boudreau (1997) trust that IC is firmly identified with human asset administration. As per Sullivan (2000) IC could be characterized as knowledge that can be changed over into benefit. Rastogi (2003) opines that IC is the synergistic exertion of a company's human capital, social capital and knowledge administration.

To condense: IC needs physical frame, It can't exist all alone, however gets an incentive from system impact, It is a claim on future assets.

IC has been characterized to incorporate consumptions on publicizing and showcasing, explore and formative exercises, human asset uses, duplicate rights, establishments, future intrigue, licenses, working rights, patent, record experts, mystery procedures, trademarks and exchange names, hierarchical structure and qualities that originated from brand names.

2.2. IC and its components

By late 90's there were various gatherings of specialists which included bookkeeping experts, administration professionals and academicians who attempted to order and group IC. IC approached with an order for ICs and reasoned that intangibles could be arranged into three classifications. Maybe this would be the primary arrangement from a non-bookkeeping point of view. In like manner impalpable asset could be characterized into three sub-classes as takes after: (1) Employee or individual fitness (2) Internal structure.(3) External structure. Another critical definition for IC and its grouping is offered by OECD (1999) which depicted IC as the monetary estimation of two classifications of immaterial assets. They are (i) Organizational (auxiliary) capital – SC.(ii)Human capital(HC).

Human capital incorporates assets inside association and assets like clients accomplices, providers which are outside to association. The SC alludes to exclusive programming frameworks, conveyance systems and supply chains. Malone and Edvinsson (1997) see IC as being made out of two segments.

- Human capital: incorporates knowledge aptitude and experience of workers.
- Structural capital: incorporates the epitome, strengthening and steady framework of human capital. Basic capital is partitioned into Organizational capital and client capital which is additionally separated into Process capital and Innovation capital.

2.3 Knowledge Management

Today, associations consider knowledge as a key lever for the upper hand and their business achievement appears to depend progressively on the capacity to survey, oversee and build up their own particular knowledge and additionally to gain new knowledge (Davenport and Prusak, 1998). Teece (1998) contends that "the upper hand of organizations in today's economy stems not from market position, but rather from hard to duplicate knowledge assets and the way in which they are sent." In the most recent decade, the focal part of knowledge, and all the more for the most part of impalpable assets, in the formation of significant worth and upper hand has been the subject of a few reviews which were led under various research streams as the Resource Based View (RBV) (Grant, 1991), the Competence Based View (CBV) (Rumelt, 1994, Barton, 1995), the Knowledge Based

Theory (KBT) (Sveiby, 2001; Grant, 1991). In those streams, capabilities are viewed as the base of an organization's capacity to get the upper hand. In addition, organization's skills are thought to be firmly connected to knowledge and its administration. Actually, KM is about overseeing knowledge assets and knowledge forms which are at the premise of advancement, support and reestablishing of authoritative capabilities (Marr, 2001). Over the most recent couple of years the writing has given a few meanings of KM (Lee and Yang, 2000; Teece, 2000; Sveiby, 2001 a) from which develop two fundamental parts of KM: (1) KM is exhibited as an arrangement of procedures and (2) it plans to make an incentive for the association.

2.4 The link between Knowledge Management and business performance

In the current years, distinctive reviews have tended to the issue of how immaterial assets add to enhance business performance and make an incentive for associations. These reviews have been centered around various parts of the exploration issue.

A current study by APQC (2001; 2002), for instance, has demonstrated while, amid the diverse periods of a KM activity, the estimation advantages are required; it has recommended some conceivable measures for the advantages. Other research has been centered around measuring and assessing the effects of KM activity on business performance. Firestone (2001) and Robinson et al. (2001) have given ways to deal with encourage the appraisal of the presumable effect of KM on performance, separately by utilizing a conceptual example of Comprehensive Benefit Estimation (CBE).

McHugh (2002), with reference to viable encounters of Unisys Corporation, has talked about instruments and yields to quantify the business effect of KM inside knowledge groups.

Different creators (Anderson 2002; Kingsley, 2002; Perkmann, 2002) have concentrated their consideration on quantitative measures of the effect of KM activities, for instance the ROI. Their exploration finds that ROI can just catch a piece of a venture's effect. This is on account of tasks dependably have unintended impacts that can't be effectively caught as a financial return.

A few scientists have investigated causal relations between KM activity usage and business performance change (Armistead 1999; Chong et al. 2000). From an observational perspective, a current review on KM inside organizations (Heisig, 2003; KPMG, 2003) has indicated distinctive effects of KM activities on financial performance, i.e. better comprehension of client's needs, change of development hierarchical capacity, increment of value, etc.

3. Research objectives and hypothesis development

IC assumes a vital part in the achievement of a wide range of associations, in other words that it is not bound to knowledge – endeavors alone. Concentrate the connection amongst IC and customary partners in financial performance assessment makes a fascinating exploration recommendation.

In the above context, the objectives of the research paper could be defined as follows:

- To estimate, evaluate and rank the IC efficiency
- To study the significant relationship between IC variables and FP variables.
- To explore the moderating effect of knowledge assets with regard to IC and financial performance

Hypotheses Development:

The present study introduces a conceptual frame work that expands on previous methodologies Willia and Firer, 2004), (Girardi, 2000); (Madininos et al 2011) to investigate the relationship between IC and financial performance and study the impact if IC on financial performance. The hypotheses of the study are presented below:

H1: a significant relationship is present between IC (Independent Variable) and FP (Dependent Variable)

H2: Knowledge Assets play a moderating role in the relationship of IC and FP.

3.2 Theoretical Framework

3.3 Research

A questionnaire has been adopted know about the responses about our proposed hypothesis. The respondents may include the employees of various public sector organizations of Bahawalpur. Questionnaire was distributed among 300 respondents in Bahawalpur, out of which 250 were found complete and correct.

3.4 Reliability Measurement

Cronbach alphas shows the internal reliability of the scale that was used in study, it is .829 in this study, as it is above .5 so it is showing that it is reliable.

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.635 ^a	.404	.397	.31390

a. Predictors: (Constant), KA, IC

A moderate positive correlation is found among the variables showing that the relationship is present and with the increase of the intellectual capital the financial performance will be enhanced.

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.893	.158		5.643	.000
	IC	.195	.060	.205	3.234	.001
	KA	.456	.054	.537	8.484	.000

a. Dependent Variable: FP

Table shows that the beta coefficient is 0.195 significant at $p < .001$ which explains that Financial performance 0.195 for every 1 unit change in IC.

Model Summary									
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.906 ^a	.820	.819	.42497128	.820	903.879	1	198	.000
2	.908 ^a	.825	.823	.42064894	.005	5.090	1	197	.025

a. Predictors: (Constant), FP

b. Predictors: (Constant), IC, KS

Coefficients ^a								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	T	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	1.560E-15	.030		.000	1.000		
	Zscore(IC)	.906	.030	.906	30.065	.000	1.000	1.000
2	(Constant)	1.473E-15	.030		.000	1.000		
	Zscore(IC)	.839	.042	.839	19.903	.000	.501	1.996
	Zscore(KA)	.095	.042	.095	2.256	.025	.501	1.996

a. Dependent Variable: Zscore(FP)

The results have found that The moderating role of knowledge assets in measuring the impact of IC of financial performance is significant and there is a strong correlation is present between this relation.

5. Conclusion

The aftereffects of this review have demonstrated that there is in truth solid and positive confirmation that organizations are overseeing IC successfully and that thus is impacting business performance decidedly. The aftereffects of this review have additionally validated past research that has occurred in various national and industry settings. It is contended that the generalizability of these outcomes is bolstered with certainty because of the full examining of the associations. The accompanying proposals are for future scholarly research:

- (1) This specific review was coordinated towards the supervisors of associations and in that capacity, information was gathered from a particular level of the authoritative progression. To test the strength of the discoveries, it is shrewd to consider looking over cutting edge representatives also sheets of chiefs.
- (2) there is sufficient chance to concentrate other knowledge-serious enterprises (e.g. programming advancement, counseling, retail). Promote observational work is expected to test how much the discoveries can be summed up to different enterprises.
- (3) A remarkable commitment of this review is the trying of IC ideas. There are a few different nations both in the Middle East and somewhere else that would profit testing these ideas in a non-Anglophonic setting.

To get the greatest advantages from the idea of IC, it ought to be considered at all four levels: singular, gathering, association and nation. In a review supported by the United Nations, (Bontis, 2004). It is vital for the administration to gather the maximum capacity of its kin by putting resources into fitting innovative framework so that human capital can be changed over (or prepared) into expanded riches and a higher expectation for everyday life. This can be accomplished for associations paying little respect to estimate (Serenko et al., 2007).

Social capital is the limit of a country to make and create business visionaries, designers, pioneers and pioneers. Social capitals enhances the capacities of people and associations for future advantages.

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Appendix

Questionnaire

The survey is being done by _____ Student of MS _____

The purpose of the survey is to collect opinions from employees about intellectual capital and financial performance provided by them.

All of the answers you provide in this survey will be kept confidential. No identifying information will be provided to anyone. The survey data will be reported in a summary only and will not identify any individual person.

This survey will take about 20 minutes to complete.

Name: _____

City: _____

Q1: Gender

- 1) Male -
- 2) Female -

Q4: Income:

- 1) Under Rs. 15,000 -
- 2) Rs. 15,000 – 25,000 -
- 3) Rs. 25,000 – 35,000 -
- 4) Rs. 35,000 – 45,000 -
- 5) Rs. 45,000 – 55,000 -

Q2 :Age

- 1) Under 20 -

- 2) 20-30 -
- 3) 30-40 -
- 4) 40-50 -
- 5) 50+ -

6) Rs. 55,000 + -

Q3: Occupation

- 1) Banker -
- 2) Doctor -
- 3) Accountant -
- 4) Engineer -
- 5) Businessman -
- 6) House wife -

Q5: Education:

- 1) under Matriculation -
- 2) Matriculation -
- 3) Intermediate –
- 4) Graduate -
- 5) Post Graduate -

Rate the following statements in terms of your answers

	<i>Strongly Agree</i>	<i>Agree</i>	<i>Undecided</i>	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Strongly Disagree</i>
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Intellectual Capital

The competence of company’s employees as a whole is equal to the most ideal level (matching with their work requirements and responsibilities)	1	2	3	4	5
The company gets the most out of its employees when they cooperate with one another in team tasks.	1	2	3	4	5
Company’s employees undergo continuous training programs every year.	1	2	3	4	5
Company’s employees continuously learn from others (colleagues and outsiders).	1	2	3	4	5
The ratio of educated personnel is on average compared with industry (no. of PhD, Master and Bachelor degrees compared with what should be).	1	2	3	4	5
Company devotes a lot of time and effort to update and develops employees’ knowledge and skills.	1	2	3	4	5
Company’s market share has been continually improving over the past few years.	1	2	3	4	5
Employees’ learning and education affect company’s productivity.	1	2	3	4	5

Knowledge Asset

It is important for the company to share knowledge with its partners.	1	2	3	4	5
The company gets as much feedback out of customers as it possibly can under different circumstances.	1	2	3	4	5
Customer knowledge is widely distributed throughout the company.	1	2	3	4	5
Data about customers are continuously updated.	1	2	3	4	5
The company has relatively complete data about the suppliers.	1	2	3	4	5
The company continually meets with customers to find out what they want from it.	1	2	3	4	5
The company has a useful and updated information system in use.	1	2	3	4	5
Company's knowledge about customers and suppliers affects company's productivity.	1	2	3	4	5
Company's data about customers and suppliers affects company's profitability.	1	2	3	4	5
Company's knowledge about customers and suppliers affects company's market value (stock value).	1	2	3	4	5

Financial Performance

Satisfaction in Business Growth including Achievement of Business Goal
Improvement in Life Standard after the business
Growth in Personal Income from the beginning of business
Improvement in Income Level when comparing before and after the business
Improvement in saving capacity and accumulation of resources from the business
Growth on net profit earnings from the business over the past five years
Improvement in Return on Investment (ROI) from the business
Improvement in Return on Assets (ROA) from the business
Growth in turnover/sales from the business over the past five years
Growth in turnover compared to the competitors over the past five years
Increasing in no. of employees from the beginning of business
Ability of industries to keep the organization's best and most talented people
Level of customer satisfaction related to business activities